

FEATURES OF MARKETING RESEARCH IN THE SERVICE SECTOR

Turayev J.¹, Suyunov F.², Mamatvaliyev X.³, Esonboyev A.⁴

Students, Karshi State University, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15621734>

Abstract. *This article is devoted to the study of the characteristic features of the organization of marketing research in the service market. The author lists the features of the service market as an object of marketing activities and concludes that it is necessary to develop the methodology of marketing research.*

Keywords: *service market, marketing, marketing research.*

Аннотация. *Данная статья посвящена изучению характерных особенностей организации маркетинговых исследований на рынке услуг. Автором перечислены особенности рынка услуг, как объекта маркетинговой деятельности и сделан вывод о необходимости развития методологии маркетинговых исследований.*

Ключевые слова: *рынок услуг, маркетинг, маркетинговые исследования.*

In the action strategy for the development of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, much attention is paid to improving the service sector, since consumers demand not only the quality of products, but also a culture of service, which is impossible without the development of this sector. Moreover, given that in developed countries, services are the leading sector of the economy of most developed countries. For example, in the countries of North Africa, Europe and Asia (Japan and South Korea), the number of employees working in the service sector exceeds the number of those employed in all other industries combined. The public and private sector in these countries accounts for 60-70% of the total national production.⁵⁴ Whereas in Uzbekistan the share of services in GDP is about 50%.

Service marketing is the action through which services offered on the market reach customers; a process recognized to assist potential consumers in assessing the services provided, allows scientific justification of decisions on the production, sale and promotion of services on the market, makes it possible to adequately assess and predict the market situation, develop a strategy and tactics of competition. The nature of the service sector, the features that distinguish a service from a material product, determines the specifics of the service market, which is considered in unity with the product market as one of the varieties, subject to the general laws of a market economy. Although the market for services has much in common with the market for goods, there are some features of market coordination due to the specific nature of the service, which requires a special approach to business and marketing activities designed to meet the demand for services.

The features of the services market are, first of all:

- in the high dynamics of market processes - the provision of services is aimed at the direct satisfaction of human needs;
- in territorial segmentation
- the forms of service provision, the demand and conditions for the functioning of enterprises for the provision of services, the demand and conditions for the operation of enterprises for the

provision of services depend on the characteristics of the territory covered by the specific market;

- in a high rate of capital turnover - one of the main advantages of a business in the service sector, which is a consequence of a shorter production cycle;

- in high sensitivity to changes in market conditions - a property caused by the impossibility of storing, storing and transporting services, as well as the temporal and spatial coincidence of their production and consumption

- in the specifics of the organization of production of services - with greater mobility, small and medium-sized enterprises that are producers of services have ample opportunities for flexible response to changes in the market situation;

- in the specifics of the process of providing services - the personal contact of the manufacturer and the consumer, on the one hand, creates conditions for the expansion of communication ties, and on the other hand, increases the requirements for professional and qualification qualities, experience, ethics and general culture of the manufacturer;

- a high degree of differentiation of services - diversification, personification and individualization of demand for services is considered as the most important incentive for innovation in the service sector, since the complex structure of demand causes the emergence of new, non-standard services; ---the search for a new service is becoming a permanent process, which is increasingly developing as market demand is saturated;

- in the uncertainty of the result of activities for the provision of services - the result of activities for the provision of services, which in many cases is subject to the influence of various qualities of the manufacturer, cannot be predetermined with sufficient accuracy; the final assessment of the result is possible only after the consumption of the service;

- services are often contrasted with products, although the role of service in industry is increasing, which may include equipment repair, after-sales service and other services related to the sale of goods. We can say that in many cases there is a product element in the service, just as with product sales there is a service element. The close interweaving of the sale of goods and the provision of services makes it difficult to distinguish and record services - the service sector is usually more protected by the state from foreign competition than the sphere of material production. Moreover, in many countries, transport and communications, financial and insurance services, science, education, health care, utilities are traditionally in full or partial state ownership or are strictly controlled or regulated by the state. The import of services, according to the governments of many countries, can pose a threat to national security and sovereignty, therefore, it is regulated more strictly than trade in goods.

Thus, the market for services in comparison with the market for goods is characterized by greater conjuncture and unpredictability. Here the question of the survival of an economic entity is acute. Among the factors shaping the market for services, one can single out: the level of development of equipment and technology, raw material potential, the level of demand for services, the level of market prices, the tax regime and the level of subsidies. The development of telecommunications and computerization reduce the need for personal contacts in the implementation of services. With technological progress, locality is being overcome, the market is becoming more open. more international. The service market most of all meets the requirements of a free market of the classical type; it lends itself the least to monopolization because the production of services is dispersed. The most common form of organizing the production of services is small businesses based on private and collective property. The profitability of the production of services is ensured not so much by economies of scale of

production as by savings in the variety and quality of services. The peculiarity of marketing research in the service sector in modern times is that it is necessary to take into account the specifics of the globalization process as the main development trend. This is a multifaceted process, as we see it, due to the structural complexity of the service markets, which has a pronounced industry specificity. In recent years, the situation has changed dramatically. Under the influence of a number of new phenomena, conditions have been formed for the active integration of many services into the global economic space. The primary role in the elimination or mitigation of traditionally high barriers on this path belongs to scientific and technological progress, primarily a powerful breakthrough in the development of information transformation of the production of services.

From the standpoint of globalization, delocalization (separation from the national soil) of many types of services, as well as a gap in the time of service production and its consumption, are especially important. It became possible to accumulate, store and transmit services over a distance, to consume them in various forms and at any time, including in real time. Many types of services have acquired the ability to be objects of foreign trade, and the world economic space has opened up for growing flows of telecommunications services, finance and education, a wide range of business and professional services, etc

Broad prospects for the globalization of services are opening up with the development of the Internet. The global network initially has a cross-border character, removes spatial and temporal barriers in international contacts between producers and consumers of services. On its basis, a radically new model of their mass consumption is being formed. The volume of transactions is steadily growing as users' access to Internet services increases, the computer literacy of the population increases, the principles and norms of legal regulation of transactions in a specific market environment are developed, measures are taken to protect intellectual property and individual rights, etc. Under the new conditions, mobile communications, a number of transport sectors (primarily aviation), and the financial sector progressed rapidly (the number of companies increased, including due to the entry of small and medium-sized firms into the market, the range of services expanded, and their prices dropped significantly). Technological and institutional shifts in these sectors not only stimulated cross-border and other forms of trade in services, but also served as a catalyst for the overall process of globalization, bringing under it a more technologically advanced and cost-effective infrastructure.

If in the past the leading positions in the structure of this sector in developed countries were occupied by trade, household, recreational and a number of other services, today a group of high-tech types of business and professional services, telecommunications, as well as education, health care, and culture have come to the fore. In combination with knowledge-intensive industries, they form, along with modernized traditional industries (trade and transport), an actively developing core of the modern economy and largely determine the dynamics, quality parameters, and competitiveness of both the service sector and the entire economy.

It is noteworthy that the "spurt" of services to foreign markets in recent years is largely associated with the expansion of "advanced" services - telecommunications, financial sector, information, computer, consulting, management, marketing, engineering and construction, auditing, educational and a number of others. This group of industries has a growing and often decisive influence on the dynamics, structural and qualitative characteristics of the internationalization of services and gives a powerful acceleration to the overall process of globalization.

Making a general conclusion, we can say that the ongoing marketing research in the service sector requires even more a more qualified approach, taking into account new trends in the global economy, which in turn requires modern personnel in the field of marketing to constantly improve their knowledge.

References

1. Official site of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan. www.stat.uz
2. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 14, 2019 No PP-4239 "On measures to develop agricultural cooperation in the field of fruit and vegetables."
3. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 11, 2019 No PP 4549 "On additional measures for further development of the fruit and vegetable and viticulture sector, the creation of a value chain in the industry."
4. James S. Johnson, Donald F. Wood, Daniel L. Wardlow, Paul R. Murphy- ml. "Modern logistics". Uchebnoe posobie. - M.: "Williams", 2015.